

Precipitation Trend Analysis for Surat District, Gujarat

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Abstract

A study of Precipitation trend analysis for total monthly rainfall over Surat District has been made. For such study, 1982 to 2017 study periods have been identified. Total 10 stations having such data have been selected for the study. This is an effort to analyse one of the most important climatic variable i.e. precipitation, for analysing the rainfall trend in the area. Monsoon in India is normally considered between June, July, August and September (JJAS). This period has been considered for the study. The daily rainfalls over the station were cumulated over the month. Non Parametric test Man Kendall test was then performed over all stations for different month. Sen's Slope was also calculated to know the magnitude of increase or decrease of rainfall. From the trend analysis, for September month most of the stations showed increase in rainfall, while for August most of them showed decreasing trend. For June and July month, some stations showed increasing, while some showed decreasing trends in rainfall. Box and Whisker plots were also derived to know about trends.

Keywords: Precipitation, Trend analysis, Climate Change, Mann-Kendall Test, Sen's Slope Estimator, Box and Whisker Plots.

1. INTRODUCTION

Precipitation trend analysis on different spatial and temporal scales has been of great concern during the past century because of the attention given to global climate change from the scientific community; they indicate a small positive global trend, even though large areas are instead characterized by negative trends (IPCC, 1996). Extreme events seem to be occurring with increasing frequency over the recent years. The focus on hydro-meteorological conditions is increasing for it holds the key for efficient management of water resources, flood management (Arun Mondal, 2012)

Guhathakurta and Rajeevan (2007) observed significant decrease in pre-monsoon rainfall for the six subdivisions viz., Gujarat Region, West M. P., East M. P., Vidarbha, Chhattisgarh and Jharkhand. However during the post-monsoon season, rainfall is increasing for almost all the sub-divisions except for the nine subdivisions. (Kumar, et al., 2010) revealed that there are significant differences in rainfall trends at the regional level.

2. MATERIALS AND METHDOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

For the said study, Surat district, located in Gujarat was selected. Surat District is located to the south of Gujarat. It shares its boundary with Bharuch, Narmada, Navsari and Tapi district. Gulf of Cambay is located to its West. According to 2011 census, the total population of Surat is 60, 79,231. Tapi, Purna and Mindola River, passes through Surat District. Surat City, being one of the most important trading centres in Textile and Diamond in India, attract many inhabitants from neighbouring states. The main source of water for Surat is Tapi River. Yearly rainfall for Surat is 1192 mm.

Figure 1. Map of Surat District

Source: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF METHODS FOR RAINFALL TREND(PRASIT G. AGNIHOTRI, May 2018)

2.2 Data and Methodology

Data from State Water Data Center (SWDC) was taken from period 1961 to 2017 was obtained. Data from total 21 rainguage stations located in Surat district was received. The data contained daily rainfall (mm) data from 1961. From this data, stations with less than 5% missing data were selected. 10 such stations were identified which had daily rainfall data, with less than 5 % missing data and continuous 30 years data. A common period 1982 to 2017 was taken for the said study. For the study, monsoon period between June to September (JJAS) was considered to understand the precipitations trends. After identifying the station, study duration and months, Man-Kendall trend analysis, Sen’s Slope analysis and Box Plotting was done.

Table 1 Latitude Longitudes of Rainguage Stations

Station Name	Latitude	Longitude
Kadod	21°13'1.81"N	73°13'10.99"E
Kholvad	21°16'30"N	72°56'55"E
Uchchhal	21°10'43' N	73°46'31' E
Ukai	21°15'25' N	73°34'50' E
Uteva	21°21'00' N	73°12'53' E
Antapur	20° 57' 02' N	73° 24' 11' E
Dhanmoli	21° 02' 17' N	73° 37' 25' E
Jamkhadi	21° 05' 25"N	73° 38' 34' E
Tichakia	21° 01' 49' N	73° 25' 37' E
Raniamba	20° 59' 07' N	73° 31' 24' E

Figure 2 Flowchart Describing Overall Methodology

2.2.1 Trend Analysis

In the present study, trend analysis has been done by using non-parametric Man- Kendall test. This is a Statistical method which is being used for studying the spatial variation and temporal trends of hydro climatic series. A non-parametric test is taken into consideration over the parametric one since it can evade the problem roused by data skew (Smith, 2000). Man-Kendall test is preferred when various Stations are tested in a single study (Hirsch, et al., 1991). Mann-Kendall test had been formulated by Mann (1945) as non-parametric test for trend detection and the test statistic distribution had been given by Kendall (1975) for testing non-linear trend and turning point. (Arun Mondal, 2012)

Box and whisker plots offer a pictorial summary of important dataset characteristics including the central tendency, dispersion, asymmetry, and extremes, arrived at through percentile rank analysis and the plotting of maximum and minimum dataset values. Since box and whisker plots display measures of central tendency and spread free from the assumption of a normal distribution, they provide an effective way of identifying asymmetrical attributes in meteorological datasets. Additionally, the underlying statistics are more resistant toward individual outliers than other methods, such as mean and standard deviation. (BANACOS, 2011)

2.2.2 The Mann-Kendall Test

The MK test is the excellent non-parametric test for identifying the presence of monotonic trend in given time series also recommended by world metrological department (Bera, 2017). The Major two advantages of the method are non-requirement of normally distribution of time series and low sensitivity in homogeneous time series (Padhiary J., et al., (2018))

The time series data X_i are assumed to follow the following model:

$$X_t = f(t_i) + \epsilon_i \quad \dots(1)$$

Where,

$f(t_i)$ = continuous monotonic increasing or decreasing function of time,

ϵ_i = residual, supposed to be from same distribution and have zero mean.

Therefore, the variance of distribution is assumed to be a constant in time. The null hypothesis(H_0) in this method is assumption of no having no trend of a time series and the alternate hypothesis is assumption of having increasing or decreasing trend of the time series(H_1).

The Mann-Kendall statistics is obtained by following formula:

$$S = \sum_{i=2}^n \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \text{sign}(x_i - x_j) \quad \dots(2)$$

Where,

S = Mann-Kendall statistics

n = number of annual values in data series (no. of data point) and it can be a smaller than the number of year in time series.

x_i and x_j = two subsets of data set

$$j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n - 1$$

$$i = j + 1, j + 2, j + 3, \dots, n \text{ and}$$

$$\text{sign}(x_i - x_j) = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{for } (x_i - x_j) < 0 \\ 0, & \text{for } (x_i - x_j) = 0 \\ 1, & \text{for } (x_i - x_j) > 0 \end{cases}$$

For $n < 10$, The absolute positive value of S is directly compared with theoretical distribution of S given by Mann and Kendall. For present study, $n \geq 10$, the data is considered to be normally distributed approximately having variance as follows;

$$\text{VAR}(S) = \frac{1}{18} [n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{p=1}^q t_p(t_p-1)(2t_p+5)] \quad \dots(3)$$

Where,

n = no. of data points

q = no. of tied groups

t_p = no. of data values in p^{th} group.

For data value $n \geq 10$, normal approximation test, also known as Z-test is generally used. For normal approximation test the both values, S and VAR(S) are used to determine z-statistics, which is given as follows;

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{(S-1)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & S > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{(S+1)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The Z-value obtained by above equation is used to access the statistically significant trend in time series, which follows normal distribution. The positive value of Z- statistics is denoting increasing trend and the

negative value of Z-statistics denotes decreasing trend. The normal distribution is followed by the Z-statistics. To test for the presence of the monotonic trend (either increasing or decreasing trend, two-tail test) at the significance level of α , for the absolute value of Z is more than $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, where $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ can be obtained from standard normal distribution table. (Bera, 2017)

2.2.3 Sen's Slope Estimator

The Sen's Slope Estimator non parametric method is useful to estimate the (change of variable per year) true slope of the present trend, also where the trend can be assumed as linear trend, which means that the value of $f(t_i)$ in equation (1) can be given as,

$$f(t) = Q + B \quad \dots(5)$$

where, Q = slope estimate and B = constant. The slope for all the data pairs is estimated first to get slope estimate Q_i in equation (5),

$$Q_i = \frac{x_j - x_k}{j - k} \quad \dots(6)$$

Where, Q_i = slope for all data value pairs x_j and x_k = data source at time j and k respectively ($j > k$) we get as many as $N = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ slope estimates of Q_i , if there are n values of x_j in time series. Therefore, the N values of Q_i are arranged from smallest to largest and the Sen's slope value can be obtained as median of the N values of Q_i . Mathematically it can be represented as,

$$Q = Q_{\left[\frac{N+1}{2}\right]}, \text{ if } N \text{ is odd and,}$$

$$Q = \frac{1}{2} \{Q_{[N/2]} + Q_{[(N+1)/2]}\}, \text{ if } N \text{ is even} \quad \dots(7)$$

At two different confidence interval $\alpha = 0.01$ and $\alpha = 0.05$, the confidence interval can be obtained as,

$$C\alpha = Z_{1-\alpha/2} * \sqrt{\text{Var}(S)} \quad \dots(8)$$

Where, $\text{Var}(S)$ can be obtained from equation 4 and $Z_{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}}$ is obtained from standard normal distribution table. The lower limit of confidence interval ($A_{\min}$) is M^{th} largest and upper limit of confidence interval ($A_{\max}$) is $(M+1)^{th}$ largest values of N ordered slope estimate in Q_i . The upper and lower limits are interpolated if the M_2 and M_1 are interpolated respectively (Bera, 2017).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Trend Analysis

Trend analysis by Mann Kendall as well as Box and Whisker plots was done to understand the trend in precipitations.

3.1.1 Man-Kendall Trend Analysis for June Month for $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.10$ Significant Level and corresponding Sen's Slope Value:

Table 2 Results of Trend Analysis for June month for rainfall time series

Station Name	Sen's Slope	Trend at 95 %	Trend at 90 %
Kadod	-1.1103	No Trend	No Trend
Kholvad	0.7136	No Trend	No Trend
Uchchhal	0.04	No Trend	No Trend
Ukai	0.412	No Trend	No Trend
Uteva	0.335	No Trend	No Trend
Antapur	-0.8	No Trend	No Trend
Dhanmoli	0.13	No Trend	No Trend
Jamkhadi	-0.06	No Trend	No Trend
Tichakia	-2.36	No Trend	No Trend
Raniamba	-2.18	No Trend	No Trend

3.1.2 Man-Kendall Trend Analysis for July Month for $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.10$ Significant Level and corresponding Sen's Slope Value

Table 3. Results of Trend Analysis for July month for rainfall time series

Station Name	Sen's Slope	Trend at 95 %	Trend at 90 %
Kadod	-2.2042	No Trend	No Trend
Kholvad	5.851	No Trend	No Trend
Uchchhal	-3.89	No Trend	No Trend
Ukai	0.981	No Trend	No Trend
Uteva	6.57	No Trend	No Trend
Antapur	-8.57	No Trend	No Trend
Dhanmoli	-0.76	No Trend	No Trend
Jamkhadi	-5.19	No Trend	No Trend
Tichakia	-4.93	No Trend	No Trend
Raniamba	-5.93	No Trend	No Trend

3.1.3 Man-Kendall Trend Analysis for August Month for $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.10$ Significant Level and corresponding Sen's Slope Value:

Table 4. Results of Trend Analysis for August month for rainfall time series

Station Name	Sen's Slope	Trend at 95 %	Trend at 90 %
Kadod	-0.8287	No Trend	No Trend
Kholvad	2.778	No Trend	No Trend
Uchchhal	-5.84	Trend Present	Trend Present
Ukai	-0.525	No Trend	No Trend
Uteva	0.428	No Trend	No Trend
Antapur	-7.01	No Trend	Trend Present
Dhanmoli	-4.12	No Trend	No Trend
Jamkhadi	-5.72	No Trend	No Trend
Tichakia	-2.51	No Trend	No Trend
Raniamba	-5.24	No Trend	Trend Present

3.1.4 Man-Kendall Trend Analysis for September Month for $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.10$ Significant Level and corresponding Sen's Slope Value:

Table 5. Results of Trend Analysis for September month for rainfall time series

Station Name	Sen's Slope	Trend at 95 %	Trend at 90 %
Kadod	2.53	No Trend	No Trend
Kholvad	5	Trend Present	Trend Present
Uchchhal	1.23	No Trend	No Trend
Ukai	2.926	No Trend	No Trend
Uteva	6.64	Trend Present	Trend Present
Antapur	0.57	No Trend	No Trend
Dhanmoli	1.29	No Trend	No Trend
Jamkhadi	1.99	No Trend	No Trend
Tichakia	1.88	No Trend	No Trend
Raniamba	1.68	No Trend	No Trend

Figure 3 Rainfall Trend at Kholvad Station from June to October month

Figure 4 Rainfall Trend at Uchchal Station from June to October month

Figure 5 Rainfall Trend at Uteva Station from June to October month

Figure 6 Rainfall Trend at Antapur Station from June to October month

Figure 7 Rainfall Trend at Raniamba Station from June to October month

3.2 Box and Whisker Plot Analysis

Since box and whisker plots display measures of central tendency and spread free from the assumption of a normal distribution, they provide an effective way of identifying asymmetrical attributes in meteorological datasets. (BANACOS, 2011). The box plots are plotted for each 10 stations for each month from June to October for rainfall to understand the rainfall variability and pattern at each station, as shown in fig (12-16).

Figure 8 Boxplot- June month

Figure 9 Boxplot - July month

Figure 10 Boxplot - August month

Figure 11 Boxplot September month

4. CONCLUSION-

From the study of precipitation trends for the given stations for the given period, it can be inferred that total monthly rainfall (in mm) for September month has shown increasing trends at all stations located in Surat District. The Sen's Slope value suggests that magnitude of increase is maximum at Uteva Station, while it's least at Antapur. Also, from the Man Kendall test for Uteva Station, it can be inferred that there is monotonic trend present with 90% as well 95% Significance. Kholvad and Uteva stations showed monotonic trend for total monthly rainfall for September month with 95% significance.

For the month of June as well as July, no stations exhibited monotonic trends at 90% or 95% significance. For August rainfall pattern, 3 stations, namely Uchchhal, Antapur and Raniamba showed monotonic trends. The Sen's Slope as well as "τ" Value suggests decrease in the rainfall trend. 8 out of 10 stations indicated decreasing trend in total monthly rainfall for August month.

From Box and Whisker plots, for June, it can be inferred that "Jamkhadi" stations showed maximum positive skewness and well as outliers. This suggests that increase in rainfall with probability of outliers in future. For July trends, Jamkhadi, Khovad, Ukai and Uteva showed upward positive skewness. Whereas Jamkhadi and Kadod has maximum outliers.

August trends from Box and Whisker plots suggest Uchchhal and Uteva stations with maximum outliers. Dhanmoli, Jamkhadi, Raniamba and Ukai showed positive upward trends, whereas Kholvad showed negative trend. For September, Jamkhadi and Raniamba showed maximum outlier values. Small boxes and long tails for September suggests more values in future may have more outlier rainfall values than the Inter Quartile Range. For September, all the stations except for Ukai showed upward positive skewness. The study may be useful in understanding the rainfall trends for Surat District. It may be helpful for future policy makers, planners, researchers for understand changes in rainfall pattern due to climate change.

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